

***In vitro* Polyploidization of *Zehneria capillacea* (Schumach.) C. Jeffrey Using Nodal Explants**

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. Author JUA designed the study. Authors JUA and CE performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol and the first draft of the manuscript, managed the analyses of the study and managed the literature searches. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Zehneria capillacea (Schumach.) C. Jeffrey is a wild diploid ($2n = 2x = 22$) andromonoecious climber that is eaten as vegetable in Nigeria. *In vitro* polyploidy induction was conducted using oryzalin as a microtubule inhibitor at various concentrations (10, 20 and 30 μM) and two time durations (24 and 48hrs). This research was conducted to develop a protocol for induction of polyploids through *in vitro* technique in order to create variability and broaden the genetic base of this species. Shoot length was significantly affected by oryzalin concentration at 24 and 48 hours treatment duration. The nodal segments immersed in 10, 20 and 30 μM oryzalin for 24 hrs had shoot lengths of 7.56 ± 0.06 cm, 7.24 ± 0.06 cm and 7.31 ± 0.07 cm respectively which were statistically similar while the shoot length of those treated for 48 hrs significantly decreased with increase in oryzalin concentration ranging from 7.02 ± 0.07 cm for 10 μM to 2.71 ± 0.11 cm for 30 μM . 10 μM oryzalin for 24 hrs and 48 hrs induced 100% $2x+4x$ and $2x+4x+8x$ cytochimera respectively. Application of 20 μM for 24 hrs induced 75% $2x+4x$ and 25% solid tetraploids while 20

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μM for 48 hrs induced 25% $2x+4x$ and 75% solid tetraploids. Application of 30 μM oryzalin for 24 hrs induced 100% $2x+4x+8x$ and 48 hrs induced 20% $2x+4x+8x$ and 80% $4x+8x$. The results obtained indicate that polyploids (tetraploid, $4x$ and octoploids, $8x$) can be induced using nodal explants from *Z. capillacea* grown *in vitro* thereby conserving and enhancing the ethno-botanical and economic values the species.

Keywords: *In vitro*; polyploidization; *Zehneria capillacea*; oryzalin; tetraploid; octoploid.

1. INTRODUCTION

Plants are the source of life for living beings, and they carry out many functions at the places where they exist. In the place they grow, plants reduce air pollution [1]; Reduce noise [2]; Increase aesthetic value [3]; have a positive psychological effect [4]; provide energy conservation [5]; prevent erosion [6]; reduce wind speed and hold the soil with their roots, thus preventing washing away of the soil with rainfalls and streams, and protect wildlife and hunting resources. Open-green areas with plantation are important activity areas for both adults and children [7].

Such advancement of the plants market made the researchers to be interested in various issues such as defining the distribution areas of plants [8]; protection of plants [9–11]; cultivation of plants [12,13]; resistance of plants to stress factors [14,15]; economic value [16]; various areas of use [2]; genetic variability of plants [6,17,18], their relationship with the environment [19,20], thus resulting in various studies on these issues.

Due to these different uses of plant, plant production is therefore of great importance to man and animals. Plants are extensively produced by seed or vegetative way. However; micro-culture techniques of production in the plant in recent years has been quite widespread [21,22,18]. These techniques have been used to improve the yield of plants [23,24], enhance/increase the chemical constituents (secondary metabolites) and medicinal values [25,26].

Polyploidy which is a condition whereby a biological cell or organism or plant has more than two sets of homologous sets of chromosomes can arise spontaneously in nature by several mechanisms, including meiotic or mitotic failures, and fusion of unreduced ($2n$) gametes [27]. Both autopolyploids in potato [28] and allopolyploids (e.g. canola, wheat, cotton) can be found among both wild and domesticated plant species. Most

polyploids display novel variation or morphologies relative to their parental species, that may contribute to the processes of speciation and eco-niche exploitation [18,27,29]. The mechanisms leading to novel variation in newly formed allopolyploids may include gene dosage effects (resulting from more numerous copies of genome content), the reunion of divergent gene regulatory hierarchies, chromosomal rearrangements, and epigenetic remodeling, all of which affect gene content and/or expression levels [29–36]. Huge explosions in angiosperms species diversity appear to have coincided with the timing of ancient genome duplications shared by many species.

In West Africa and Nigeria in particular, *Zehneria* species are used for several purposes including food [37,38], treatment of tapeworm and as sedatives [39], taken by nursing mothers to aid postpartum recovery [40,41] and to induce abortion [42]. This plant is sourced from the wild by the locals. The impacts of anthropogenic activities have led to depletion in the biodiversity of Niger Delta [31]. In view of the biodiversity loss and the ethno-botanical potential of this *Zehneria* species there is need to broaden the genetic base by creating variability through *in vitro* polyploid induction. This study was therefore carried out to induce polyploids in *Zehneria capillacea* using nodal explants from *in vitro* plantlets and oryzalin as a doubling agent.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

This study was carried out in the tissue culture laboratory of the BioScienc Center, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture Ibadan, Nigeria.

2.1 Culture Medium Preparation

The medium formulation described by Murashige and Skoog [43] referred to as MS medium was selected as the optimal culture medium for *in vitro* studies. The medium was supplemented with plant growth regulators. The plant growth regulators used in this experiment were 6-benzyl

amino purine (BAP), and indole-3-acetic acid (IAA). The preparation of the oryzalin, shoot multiplication, root induction, culture incubation, Flow Cytometry (FCM) Analysis using Partec PAS 11 flow cytometer (Partec GmbH, Germany), plant acclimatization and establishment is as stated in [18,44,45].

2.2 *In vitro* Polyploidization

The *in vitro* mitotic polyploidization performed under aseptic conditions involved culture of donor plants, preparation of nodal segments, application of microtubule inhibitor and culture of treated nodes. *In vitro* plantlets were cultured on hormone free Murashege and Skoog (MS) medium for three weeks in a culture chamber. The experimental design was a 2-way factorial design with four concentrations of oryzalin (0, 10, 20 and 30 μ M) and two time duration (24 and 48 hours). Nodal segments were excised from the upper part (2nd nodal segment under the shoot apex) of the *in vitro* grown plants, defoliated and submerged in sterilized baby food jars containing 10mls of aqueous solutions of the various concentrations of oryzalin. Two jars with ten nodes each were used for the two treatment duration giving a total of 20 nodes per treatment. The jars containing the explants were continuously agitated on a Gallenkamp orbital shaker at 90 rpm for the given treatment duration after which the oryzalin solution was poured out and the nodes rinsed 5 - 6 times with sterile distilled water under a laminar flowhood. The treated rinsed nodal segments were transferred into fresh gelrite-solidified hormone free MS medium and cultured under standard conditions [18]. After two weeks, necrotic stem tips were trimmed off from the nodal segments and sub-cultured into fresh gelrite-solidified MS medium supplemented with 1.0 mg/l BAP to obtain shoots for ploidy determination. The nodal segments were visually examined after one month to determine percentage contamination/survival, phenolics exudation and overall growth response. The nodal segments of 5-explants that survived and proliferated were analyzed for ploidy level using a flow cytometer [44,46].

2.3 Data Collection

The parameters evaluated were percentage of explants survival, seedling length, ploidy level and induction frequency after 21 days.

The induction frequency of plant was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Frequency induction (\%)} = (\text{No. of explants showing response} / \text{Total No. of explants inoculated}) \times 100$$

The number of plantlets that survived were recorded and the percentage calculated.

2.4 Statistical Analysis

All the data obtained from the *in vitro* studies were expressed as mean \pm SE and were subjected to one way analysis of variance and Duncan's multiple range test (DMRT) to test the significance of the treatment difference.

3. RESULTS

The treatment of nodal segments with lateral buds in various concentrations of aqueous solution of oryzalin for 24 and 48 hours revealed a significant interaction between oryzalin concentration and treatment duration. It was observed that all the micro-shoots in the control had mean shoot lengths of 15.53 ± 0.08 cm and 15.51 ± 0.07 cm which differed significantly from that exhibited by the oryzalin treated shoots (Table 1 and Fig. 1). Shoot length was significantly affected by oryzalin concentration and 48 hours treatment duration. The nodal segments immersed in 10, 20 and 30 μ M oryzalin for 24 hrs had shoot lengths of 7.56 ± 0.06 cm, 7.24 ± 0.06 cm and 7.31 ± 0.07 cm respectively which were statistically similar while the shoot length treated with 10 μ M and 30 μ M oryzalin for 48 hrs are significantly shorter with values ranging from 7.02 ± 0.07 cm for 10 μ M to 2.71 ± 0.11 cm for 30 μ M respectively (Table 1 and Fig. 2). These were significantly shorter than those treated for 24 hrs time duration.

Factors that inhibit culture growth such as contamination, hyper-hydricity and phenolic exudation were not observed in all the treatments throughout the culture period. Necrosis was observed in the oryzalin treated micro-shoots after two weeks of transfer to MS solid medium but only 5% of the micro-shoots treated with 30 μ M oryzalin for 48 hrs were lost to necrosis (Table 1).

3.1 Flow Cytometer (FCM) Analysis

The three groups of ploidy level observed were diploids, tetraploids and three classes of

mixoploids (2x+4x, 2x+4x+8x and 4x+8x). The control plants had a mean relative fluorescence (MRF) of 49.18 – 49.67 while the tetraploids had MRF values (95 – 99) which double that of the diploid samples. The mixoploids had histograms with two or three distinct MRF values (Fig. 3, Table 2).

Table 1. Effect of different concentrations of oryzalin and treatment duration on shoot length of *Z. capillacea* in MS proliferation medium

Treatments	Oryzalin conc. (µM)	Treatment duration (Hours)	Shoot length (cm)*	Shoot survival (%)
T ₁	0	24	15.53 ± 0.11 ^a	100
T ₂	10	24	7.56 ± 0.11 ^b	100
T ₃	20	24	7.24 ± 0.08 ^b	100
T ₄	30	24	7.31 ± 0.09 ^b	100
T ₅	0	48	15.51 ± 0.10 ^a	100
T ₆	10	48	7.02 ± 0.09 ^c	100
T ₇	20	48	5.67 ± 0.10 ^d	100
T ₈	30	48	2.71 ± 0.16 ^d	95

*Means followed by the same letter within columns are not significantly different using DMRT at the 5% level of significance

Fig. 1. Effect of different concentrations of oryzalin on micro-shoot development of *Zehneria capillacea*. (Nodal segments were treated for 24 hours)

Fig. 2. Effect of different concentrations of oryzalin on micro-shoot development of *Zehneria capillacea*. (Nodal segments were treated for 48 hours)

Table 2. Ploidy level, MRF values, coefficient of variation and polyploidization efficiency induced by various oryzalin concentration on *Z. capillacea*

Oryzalin conc. (μM)	Induction efficiency (%)					MRF*	CV** (%)
	2x	4x	2x+4x	2x+4x+8x	4x+8x		
<i>In vitro</i> induction (24 hrs)							
0	100	0	0	0	0	49.18	2.3
10	0	0	100	0	0	50, 99	1.7, 2.8
20	0	0	75	25	0	48, 96	1.6, 1.3
30	0	0	0	100	0	47, 95, 193	1.4, 1.5
<i>In vitro</i> induction (48 hrs)							
0	100	0	0	0	0	49.67	1.5
10	0	0	0	100	0	50, 99, 196	1.7, 2.8, 2.2
20	0	75	25	0	0	48, 96	1.6, 1.8
30	0	0	0	20	80	48, 97, 193	1.3, 1.4, 1.5

MRF* = Mean Relative Fluorescence and CV** = means coefficient of variation

The percentage of various ploidy levels induced by different oryzalin concentration, the MRF values, coefficient of variation and polyploidization efficiency are presented in Table 2. The *in vitro* application of 10 μM oryzalin for 24hrs and 48hrs induced 100% 2x+4x and

2x+4x+8x cytochimera respectively. Application of 20 μ M for 24 hrs induced 75% 2x+4x and 25% solid tetraploids while 20 μ M for 48 hrs induced 25% 2x+4x and 75% solid tetraploids.

Application of 30 μ M oryzalin for 24 hrs induced 100% 2x+4x+8x and 48hrs induced 20% 2x+4x+8x and 80% 4x+8x (Table 2).

Fig. 3. Flow cytometric profiles of *Z. capillacea* plants treated with oryzalin (The peaks of the horizontal y-axis correspond to relative nuclear DNA content, which is expressed as the fluorescence intensity (FLI). The number of nuclei is shown on the vertical x-axis: (A) solid tetraploid 4x, (B) mixoploid 2x+4x, (C) mixoploid 2x+4x+8x, (D) mixoploid 4x+8x, (E) control diploid 2x, (Diploid/control nuclei was set to channel 50 with tetraploids resolving at channel 100, Octoploids at channel 200)

4. DISCUSSION

The increase in nuclear ploidy affects the structural and anatomical characteristics of the plant [18]. In general, polyploidy results in increased leaf and flower size, stomatal density, cell size and chloroplast count [47], decrease in stomatal density and increase in stomatal size [18]. These phenomena are collectively referred to as the gigas effect [33]. Physiological changes are also known to accompany genome duplication. These mainly result from change of metabolism resulting in a general increase in secondary metabolites [25]. This property has found application in the breeding of medicinal herbs in the production of pharmaceuticals. Hybrid vigor resulting from interspecific crosses in allopolyploids is one of the most exploited advantages of polyploid in plant breeding.

Genome doubling under *in vitro* controlled conditions is a tool for exploration and domestication of wild germplasm [48]. *In vitro* polyploidization has become an almost routinely applied breeding technique in many ornamentals and other crops [49,50]. In watermelon, induced autotetraploids are used for the production of seedless triploid hybrids [51]. *In vitro* polyploidization can be achieved through the addition of chemicals that inhibit mitotic spindle fibre formation directly into the culture medium [50,52], as an aqueous solution onto nodal segments [53]. Success has been reported using embryogenic and non-embryogenic callus [54,55], nodal segments [56], cotyledons [57] and hypocotyls [52]. *In vitro* polyploidization has been induced in many species such as banana [58,59], *Alocasia* [60], *Bacopa monnieri* [53] and cotton [61].

Oryzalin is often more effective than colchicine because it has a higher affinity for plant tubulins [62-64]. The ploidy level of several plant species which have been altered using oryzalin include *Pyrus* L. [65], *Solanum* L. [66], *Tulipa* L. [67], *Rosa* L. [68] and *Miscanthus sinensis* Anderson [69]. Treating shoot apices of *M. sinensis* in 15 μM oryzalin solution for 96 hours was the most effective treatment for inducing polyploids while 60 μM oryzalin prevented callus initiation in immature inflorescences of *M. sinensis* that were cultured *in vitro* [69]. Bouvier [18] observed that 200 μM – 300 μM concentrations of oryzalin were required to induce polyploidy in *Pyrus* L while in *Solanum* L. the most effective treatment for tetraploid induction was 24 hour treatment with 28.8 μM oryzalin solution applied to apical buds [66]. In agriculture and horticulture, polyploid

induction have been used to improve plant yield and fruit size [70], medicinal values of plants, resistance to pest, flower colour, size and number [71-74].

In the present study, we used an *in vitro* method to investigate the effect of oryzalin treatment at different concentrations and time durations on polyploid induction in *Z. capillacea*. The *in vitro* application of 10 μM oryzalin for 24hrs induced 2x+4x, 20 μM oryzalin for 24 and 48hrs to nodal segments produced the optimal number (75%) of solid tetraploids while application of 30 μM for 48hrs resulted in stunted shoots that redoubled yielding cytochimeras with 4x+8x cells. This suggests that for a breeder whose interest is solid tetraploids, the best treatment for him is to apply 20 μM oryzalin for 24 and 48 hrs and 10 μM oryzalin for 24 hrs to nodal segments of *Z. capillacea*. On the other hand, for tetraploids and octoploids, the breeder will pretreat the nodal segment of the explant in 30 μM for 48hrs. This is consistent with reports that high concentrations and prolonged exposure times result in lethal or redoubling effects [75]. Also among the Cucurbitaceae, *In vitro* technique has been well demonstrated and the regeneration of plants has been reported from excised plant parts such as hypocotyls [34], cotyledons [34–36,76–81], shoot tips [82,83], nodal segments [84–86], leaf [80,87–89], embryonal axis [90] and anthers [91].

In other plant families and genera, ploidy manipulation is considered as a valuable tool in genetic improvement of many plants including *Solanum* spp. [92], citrus [93], pomegranate [94], *Allium* spp. [95] and azaleas [96]. An attempt to increase ploidy level has been conducted with different objectives in various plants. In citrus, tetraploid (4x) parents were produced to create seedless triploids by crossing (4x) and (2x) parents [93]. In medicinal plants, such as, *Scutellaria* spp. [97] and *Artemisia* spp. [98], tetraploidy increases the amounts of the secondary metabolites, baicalin and artemisinin. In *Azalea*, chromosome doubling was used to obtain new ornamental characteristics [96]. In *Acacia mearnsii*, tetraploids were produced for increased bark and tannin production and for generating sterile triploids [99]. In addition, the polyploids also provide a wider germplasm base for breeding studies [100].

The enhanced production of secondary metabolites such as alkaloids and terpenes in polyploids may concurrently offer resistance to pests and pathogens [101,102]. Experiments with diploid *Glycine tabacina*, a forage legume

established that 42% of the tetraploid plants were resistant to leaf rust, *Phakopsora pachyrhizi* compared to 14% of the diploid plants [27]. Similar results were observed while comparing resistance to insects and the clover eel nematode between *Trifolium pratense* (red clover) tetraploids and diploids [103]. Given these possible beneficial consequences, chemical polyploidization has become an almost routinely applied breeding technique in many ornamentals and other crops [104,105]. Breeders have harnessed the process of chromosome doubling through induced polyploidy to produce superior crops. For example in watermelon, induced autotetraploids are used for the production of seedless triploid hybrids [106]. The polyploid induction of *Z. capillacea* could enhance its medicinal properties. This is attributed to the fact that increase in ploidy level corresponds to increase in chemical constituents of plants [101,102].

In vitro polyploid induction provide a more controlled standardized environment, increases efficiency and decreases the occurrence of chimaeras compared with conventional *in vivo* methods [107,108]. For *in vitro* induction, a reliable regeneration system must be established and potential explants that are commonly utilized are shoot tips [61,109] and nodal segments [76,110] because of their regeneration ability and lower levels of somaclonal variation than calli [55] and somatic embryos [50].

5. CONCLUSION

The finding of this work indicates that this species can be grown *In vitro* and for efficient induction of solid 2x+4x, the nodal explant from *Z. capillacea* should be treated with 10 or 20 µM of oryzalin for 24 hrs and 20 µM for 48 hrs were the best treatments while for 2x+4x+8x, 10µM and 30 µM oryzalin for 48rs were the best treatments. Also the conservation, ethnobotanical and economic values of *Z. capillacea* could be enhanced through *In vitro* culture and polyploidization.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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